

Identifying Anomalous Group Quarters Counts using American Community Survey Data

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Abstract

The Census Bureau defines group quarters (GQs) as places where people live or stay in a group living arrangement that is owned or managed by an organization providing housing or services for the residents. A single large GQ can make up a significant proportion of a small area's population. For this reason, errors in the GQ counts can be quite visible. Errors in the initial reported counts can arise due to issues in the field, measurement error, or problems with the group quarters frame.

This paper explores methods for identifying tracts with anomalous group quarters counts for review during data collection or processing for the census. American Community Survey (ACS) data at the tract level are used to detect potential errors or anomalies in the GQ counts. The assumption is that the annual ACS group quarters population estimates from the previous decade can provide a measure of the magnitude of the group quarters population in a tract, which can then be used to determine a plausible range for reported counts.

Key Words: group quarters, measurement error, outlier detection

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1. Introduction

The Census Bureau defines group quarters (GQs) as places where people live or stay in a group living arrangement that is owned or managed by an organization providing housing or services for the residents. A single large GQ can make up a significant proportion of a small area's population. For this reason, errors in the GQ counts can be quite visible. Errors in the initial reported counts can arise due to issues in the field, measurement error, or problems with the group quarters frame.

During the 2020 Census, an extensive data review was implemented to find and correct issues that originated during data collection and processing (Devine, et al., 2021). As expected, during this review, anomalies were encountered, and corrective action was taken (Thieme, 2021). For group quarters specifically, the actions taken included additional outreach to approximately 10,000 GQs and an imputation operation (Stempowski and Christy, 2021). GQs were especially impacted by the unprecedented nature of conducting a census during a pandemic, as the group quarters population includes college students living in university housing and nursing home residents, among other groups.

This paper explores using tract-level estimates of the group quarters population to determine a plausible range for GQ population in each tract, prior to the next census. Using these bounds along with modeled counts for each GQ would present a means to review and correct issues in an earlier time frame, prior to the completion of data collection. Modeling the counts for individual GQs is beyond the scope of this paper. The objective is to construct plausible bounds with which the

modeled GQ counts can be compared and replaced by actual counts during data collection and processing.

2. Background

The 2020 Census counted 8.2 million people residing in around 250,000 group quarters (Koerber and Wilson, 2021). The census counts were released down to the block level and represent the most detailed information available for the group quarters population until the next census. Presented in Table 1 are the seven major types of group quarters (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022a). Some of the major types of GQs can be broken down into more detailed categories which are included in Table 1.

Table 1: Major GQ Types

Major GQ Type	Detailed Types
Correctional Facilities for Adults	Correctional Residential Facilities Federal Detention Centers Federal and State Prisons Local Jails and Other Municipal Confinement Facilities Military Disciplinary Barracks and Jails
Juvenile Facilities	Correctional Facilities Intended for Juveniles Group Homes for Juveniles (non-correctional) Residential Treatment Centers for Juveniles (non-correctional)
Nursing Facilities/Skilled Nursing Facilities	
Other Health Care Facilities	Hospitals with Patients Who Have No Usual Home Elsewhere In-Patient Hospice Facilities Mental (Psychiatric) Hospitals and Psychiatric Units in Other Hospitals Military Treatment Facilities with Assigned Patients Residential Schools for People with Disabilities
College/University Student Housing	
Military Group Quarters	
Other Noninstitutional Facilities	Emergency and Transitional Shelters (with Sleeping Facilities) for People Experiencing Homelessness Group Homes Intended for Adults Residential Treatment Centers for Adults Religious Group Quarters Workers' Group Living Quarters and Job Corps Centers

The 2020 Census GQ enumeration consisted of two parts. During the 'advance contact' operation, GQs were contacted to verify contact information, collect expected counts for Census Day, and determine the method of enumeration. For the GQ enumeration itself, GQs were offered three response options (Stempowski and Christy, 2021):

- eResponse. The GQ electronically transfers data to the Census Bureau in a standardized template.
- Paper-based. The GQ submits a paper listing (facility administrative records with resident information) to field staff or census takers drop off and pick up completed individual census questionnaires.
- In-person. Census takers conduct in-person interviews with residents of the GQ to complete their individual census questionnaires.

Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, field operations were suspended and plans for enumerating GQs were adjusted. In-person work was pushed back to July 1st and concluded on September 3rd (Stempowski and Christy, 2021).

Research is currently underway to modernize the group quarters enumeration process for the 2030 Census (U.S. Census Bureau, 2023a). Therefore, the operations and enumeration methods for the next census may be different from the previous census.

While census releases represent the most detailed and comprehensive data about the group quarters population, the American Community Survey (ACS) releases yearly estimates of the total GQ population and characteristics of this population for states and small areas. These estimates are produced via sampling from an enhanced GQ frame. The enhanced frame is constructed from the final universe of GQs from the previous census, with additional updates from ongoing operations. The frame also contains a modeled or collected population size for each GQ. These population counts are used as weighting controls at the tract, county, and state levels. Additionally, weights for GQ persons are controlled to estimates from the Population Estimates Program (PEP). The PEP estimates contain controls by state and major group quarters type. (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022b). For information regarding the PEP methodology, refer to U.S. Census Bureau, 2023b.

The methodology for creating small-area GQ estimates in the ACS relies on an imputation strategy to ensure representation within counties and tracts. Selected not-in-sample GQ facilities receive imputed person records which are treated as sampled records during weighting and estimation. This method was implemented for the first time during the 2011 data year, in response to substantial variation found in substate estimates of the GQ population (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022b). Evaluations at the time found that the new methodology was an improvement over the previous design-based estimates of the GQ total population in each tract (Asiala and Beaghen, 2012). Overall, the small area estimates of the GQ population are subject to errors that can arise due to sampling, imputation, timing of updates to the enhanced frame, and the limitations in the PEP methodology. However, these estimates represent the best data we have about GQ population at the tract level between censuses.

3. Data

For this paper, I used publicly available data¹ to avoid the risk of unauthorized disclosure. I used two sets of five-year estimates from the ACS for survey years 2014-2018 and 2009-2013. The first set of five-year estimates were selected to simulate the census environment, where the year ending in 8 represents the last ACS five-year release prior to the start of data collection for the census. The 2009-2013 five-year estimates were selected to have two non-overlapping periods of estimates. While these estimates are subject to sampling, imputation, and other errors, the idea is that they provide two measures of magnitude of the GQ population within the tract over a decade. For brevity, I'll refer to the five-year estimates as 2018 and 2013 estimates, although they represent data for all five years.

Additionally, the 2010 Census data for each tract provides not only the total GQ population, but the population in each of the GQ types in Table 1.

Note that over the decade there were changes to tract geography and labels in the ACS data (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022c). These were accounted for by reverting 2013 and 2018 tract geography to 2010 Census tract geography. For the most part, these changes were straightforward as only the geography ID changed. However, for some tracts, there were more complicated conversions necessary. For example, in Oneida County, New York, the 2010 census tract 9402.00 forms a

¹ Data are available at data.census.gov, in the following tables: (B26001 | Group Quarters Population, ACS 5-Year Estimates Detailed) and (PCT20 | Group Quarters Population by Group Quarters Type, 2010: Dec Summary File 1).

portion of the 2011 census tract 0249.00. Part of 2010 Census tract 0230.00 forms a portion of the 2011 census tract 0249.00. The other part of 2011 census tract 0230.00 forms a portion of the 2011 Census tract 0230.00. To account for this, the 2013 and 2018 GQ population estimates for census tracts 0249.00 and 0230.00 were split according to the proportion of the GQ population in 2010 Census tracts 9402.00 and 0230.00. After adjusting for changes to geography, there were 74,001 tracts in the data set, including tracts in all 50 states, Washington D.C., and Puerto Rico.

4. Creating Plausible Bounds

My aim was to create a range of plausible counts for each tract, using these data that were available prior to the census year. Given that the five-year ACS estimates are averaged over the entire period, we don't have yearly estimates at the tract-level with which to do a time series analysis. However, because we have two non-overlapping estimates from the previous decade, we may be able to use the relationship between them to create bounds.

First, I examined the tract GQ populations for 2013 and 2018. Figure 1 shows the distributions for both years are similar and highly skewed. Note that the graph excludes tracts for which either of the estimates are equal to zero – 28,828 tracts. It also excludes tracts for which the estimates are larger than 3,000; 348 tracts for 2013 and 364 tracts for 2018. Given the highly skewed nature of these data, I considered methods typically used in establishment surveys for identifying anomalies.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 1: Tract-level GQ population estimates from five-year American Community Survey

Many of the outlier detection methods in establishment surveys rely on ratio comparisons. For micro-level editing, the ratios used are between different data items collected in the same survey – e.g., revenue and expenses, or the ratio of the same item at different time periods. Thompson (2007) explores ratio comparisons for macro-level editing of estimates from the U.S. Census Bureau's Annual Capital Expenditures Survey.

Given the two non-overlapping estimates of the GQ population for each tract, I explored applying some of the techniques investigated in Thompson (2007) to group quarters data.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 2: Tract-level GQ population estimates from five-year American Community Survey – logarithmic scale

Figure 2 presents the relationship between the 2013 and 2018 estimates. Note that I am presenting these data with both the x- and y-axes transformed to the logarithmic scale. Plotting the data this way makes it easier to see the distribution as both sets of estimates are highly skewed.

For each method examined, I created plausible bounds as a function of the most recent estimate for the tract. In practice, this would involve estimating parameters of the function from the two prior time periods and then applying those parameters to create plausible bounds using the more recent estimate. Essentially, the relationship between the 2013 and 2018 ACS estimates is carried forward and assumed to be a plausible proxy for the relationship between the 2018 ACS estimate and the 2020 Census value. Note again that the ACS estimates are averages over a five-year period; the 2018 ACS estimate does not represent that year, but the years 2014 through 2018.

The 2020 Census values are not included in this paper due to differences in tabulation tracts between the 2020 Census and the 2010 Census tabulation tracts used in the ACS data. Internally, microdata for the 2020 Census includes 2010 tabulation tracts and thus data could be flagged on that basis.

Each method involves setting a hyperparameter which controls the width of the plausible bounds. I explored the choice of hyperparameter by examining the data in three ways. First, I examined the bounds graphically to verify that they adequately fit the distribution. Second, I calculated bounds for a set of GQ populations that are ‘typical’ to determine if they are indeed ‘plausible’. Typical GQ population sizes are 1, 10, 100, 1,000 and 10,000. Finally, I examined how many tracts fell outside of the bounds in the current data set. These are not anomalies in that they are published ACS estimates – they most likely represent false positives for each method. One could set parameters to reduce these false positives to zero but that would create bounds so wide they are not likely ‘plausible’.

4.1 Ordinary Least Squares Regression

Given the apparent linear relationship between the estimates at the two different time periods, I started with simple regression models. While I explored robust regression methods, the resulting bounds were not substantially different from ordinary least squares. I used the following model:

$$Y_i = \hat{\beta}X_i + \varepsilon_i, \varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \hat{\sigma}^2) \tag{1}$$

where,

Y_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2014-2018 ACS five-year estimates.

X_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2009-2013 ACS five-year estimates.

The upper and lower plausible bounds are formed by multiplying the residual standard error by a hyperparameter – that is, a parameter set by examining the data. I fit the regression model using only tracts with positive (i.e., non-zero) estimates for both time periods.

$$LB_{OLS}(Y_i) = \hat{\beta}Y_i - d * \hat{\sigma} \tag{2}$$

$$UB_{OLS}(Y_i) = \hat{\beta}Y_i + d * \hat{\sigma} \tag{3}$$

where,

Y_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2014-2018 ACS five-year estimates.

d is a hyperparameter.

Figure 3 displays the OLS Regression plausible bounds on the estimates plotted in Figure 2. This plot shows that these bounds allow a large relative change for tracts with smaller GQ populations while enforcing a smaller relative change for tracts with larger GQ populations.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 3: OLS regression plausible bounds on ACS tract-level GQ population estimates for selected values of d – logarithmic scale

Table 2 contains the plausible bounds for different estimates in the range of the 2018 ACS tract-level GQ population estimates. It is difficult to determine from this table which value for d would be optimal.

Table 3 presents counts of tracts where the 2018 GQ population estimates would be considered ‘anomalies’ based on the 2013 GQ population estimate using this method. Again, these represent false positives. At first glance, the number of false positives seems high, but even the tightest bounds only flag 706 of the 74,001 tracts as anomalous.

Table 2: OLS regression plausible bounds for different tract-level GQ population estimates

Plausible Bounds - ($LB_{OLS}(Y_i); UB_{OLS}(Y_i)$)						
2018 ACS						
Estimate(Y_i)	d = 3	d = 4	d = 5	d = 6	d = 7	d = 8
1	(0; 458)	(0; 610)	(0; 762)	(0; 914)	(0; 1,066)	(0; 1,219)
10	(0; 467)	(0; 619)	(0; 771)	(0; 923)	(0; 1,075)	(0; 1,228)
100	(0; 557)	(0; 709)	(0; 862)	(0; 1,014)	(0; 1,166)	(0; 1,318)
1,000	(550; 1,463)	(398; 1,616)	(246; 1,768)	(94; 1,920)	(0; 2,072)	(0; 2,224)
10,000	(9,611; 10,524)	(9,459; 10,676)	(9,307; 10,829)	(9,155; 10,981)	(9,002; 11,133)	(8,850; 11,285)

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Table 3: OLS Regression counts of 2018 ACS tract-level GQ population estimates that are ‘out-of-bounds’

2018 Tract ‘Anomalies’			
d	Low	High	Total
3	320	386	706
4	216	259	475
5	151	191	342
6	102	141	243
7	74	105	179
8	54	66	120

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

The OLS method is straightforward and is not very different from setting a limit on the absolute change in the estimate between time periods. This is because the value for $\hat{\beta}$ is so close to one for the chosen time periods. Flagging anomalies based on the absolute change is simple and may be useful for creating plausible bounds based on the most recent ACS estimate. Because we are concerned about over- or under-coverage of person counts, a difference of 1,000 people in a tract would be worth reviewing whether the most recent ACS estimate was 50 or 5,000. Additionally, it is possible that during census operations, one or more GQs are enumerated that were not included in the ACS enhanced frame. The size of these additional GQs may have nothing to do with the size of the GQ population initially in the tract. In that way, imposing a limit on the absolute change makes more sense for GQs than for economic data where a change in revenue, expenses, or some other value may be dependent on the size of the business. However, we may want to consider the relative difference for a population that should remain relatively stable, e.g., a tract with a college or a prison.

4.2 Asymmetric Fences

The next method I examined was asymmetric fences. This method focuses on the ratio between the two time periods, using the differences between quartiles. Again, with this method a hyperparameter can be chosen by examining the data graphically. In this case, the hyperparameter k controls the width of the bounds around the ratios:

$$r_i = \frac{Y_i}{X_i} \quad (4)$$

$$LB_R = q_{25} - k * (r_M - q_{25}) \quad (5)$$

$$UB_R = q_{75} + k * (q_{75} - r_M) \quad (6)$$

where,

Y_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2014-2018 ACS five-year estimates.

X_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2009-2013 ACS five-year estimates.

q_{25} is the first quartile of r .

r_M is the median of r .

k is a hyperparameter.

The plausible bounds are created by carrying the bounds of the ratios forward and then multiplying by the latest estimate:

$$LB_{AF}(Y_i) = Y_i * LB_R \quad (7)$$

$$UB_{AF}(Y_i) = Y_i * UB_R \quad (8)$$

where,

Y_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2014-2018 ACS five-year estimates.

$LB(r)$ is the lower bound on the ratio.

$UB(r)$ is the upper bound on the ratio.

The distribution of the ratios is highly skewed. A transformation was applied using the square root of the ratio to create LB_R and UB_R . These values were then squared before determining the bounds for the population value. Figure 4 displays the distribution of the ratios before and after transformation.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 4: Ratios of tract-level GQ population estimates from 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 five-year American Community Survey

Figure 5 depicts the asymmetric fences bounds applied to the ACS tract-level GQ population estimates. The graph indicates that this method may have a bias of flagging estimates as too low across the range of GQ population sizes. For smaller GQ populations, i.e., less than 100, there is a large proportion of estimates that are also flagged as too high.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 5: Asymmetric fences plausible bounds on ACS Tract-level GQ population estimates for selected values of k – logarithmic scale

Table 4 and Table 5 contain plausible bounds for different GQ population estimates, and ‘anomalies’ in the 2018 GQ population estimates according to the asymmetric-fences method. For large GQ populations, the upper bounds for a tract with a population of 10,000 are extreme for all of the values of k examined. Likewise, the lower bound seems too low. With the hyperparameter k set to 3, a tract with 10,000 people in GQs could decrease that population by 6,000 without being flagged. This would be a change in the population worth examining. At the same time, the upper bound is quite low for a tract with a GQ population of 1 or 10. These bounds could easily be exceeded without any error in the data. Indeed, Table 5 shows quite high counts of ‘anomalies’ using this method.

Table 4: Asymmetric fences plausible bounds for different tract-level GQ population estimates

Plausible Bounds - ($LB_{AF}(Y_i); UB_{AF}(Y_i)$)						
2018 ACS Estimate(Y_i)	$k = 3$	$k = 4$	$k = 5$	$k = 6$	$k = 7$	$k = 8$
1	(0; 3)	(0; 3)	(0; 4)	(0; 4)	(0; 5)	(0; 6)
10	(4; 27)	(3; 32)	(2; 38)	(1; 44)	(0; 51)	(0; 58)
100	(37; 269)	(26; 321)	(16; 378)	(9; 440)	(4; 506)	(1; 577)
1,000	(373; 2,691)	(256; 3,215)	(161; 3,785)	(88; 4,401)	(37; 5,064)	(7; 5,773)
10,000	(3,733; 26,914)	(2,560; 32,148)	(1,608; 37,846)	(877; 44,010)	(365; 50,638)	(74; 57,731)

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Table 5: Asymmetric fences counts of 2018 ACS tract-level GQ population estimates that are ‘out-of-bounds’

2018 Tract ‘Anomalies’			
<i>k</i>	Low	High	Total
3	6,433	1,403	7,836
4	4,851	1,127	5,978
5	3,131	978	4,109
6	1,927	892	2,819
7	773	832	1,605
8	92	791	883

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

The asymmetric fences method seems unsuitable for the GQ count data. While it is appealing to use the relative change between time periods to set bounds, there is a large disparity in a plausible relative change for a small GQ population versus a large GQ population. An increase of the GQ population by 100% for a tract with a previous count of 50 people is much more plausible than the same relative increase for a tract with a count of 10,000 people. For that reason, we need to scale the relative change to the magnitude of the tract population.

4.2 Hidiroglou-Berthelot

Finally, I considered the Hidiroglou-Berthelot method (Hidiroglou-Berthelot, 1986). With this method, the magnitude of the GQ population is taken into account in determining an allowable relative change.

This method involves transforming the ratios in order to create a symmetric distribution.

$$S_i = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{r_M}{r_i} & 0 < r_i < r_M \\ \frac{r_i}{r_M} - 1 & r_i > r_M \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where,

r_i is the ratio of the 2018 and 2013 GQ population in tract i .

S_i is the transformed ratio for tract i .

r_M is the median of r .

After the ratios have been symmetrized, an effect size is calculated by multiplying the transformed ratio by a term, $\{\max(Y_i, X_i)\}^U$, representing the magnitude of the GQ population size in the tract. The hyperparameter U controls how much the effect size is scaled by the magnitude of the GQ population size. Typically, U takes a value between 0 and 1 (Hidiroglou-Berthelot, 1986). Figure 6 displays the ratios on the left side of Figure 4 after the symmetrizing transformation and after the calculation of effect size.

$$E_i = S_i * \{\max(Y_i, X_i)\}^U \quad (10)$$

where,

E_i is the effect size for tract i .

S_i is the transformed ratio for tract i .

Y_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2014-2018 ACS five-year estimates.

X_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2009-2013 ACS five-year estimates.

U is a hyperparameter.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 6: Ratios of tract-level GQ population estimates from 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 five-year American Community Survey after symmetrizing transformation (left) and effect size calculation (right) ($U = 0.75$).

Next, boundaries for the effect sizes are calculated according to the following formulas. Note the similarity of these formulas to equations (5) and (6), the boundaries for the ratios with the asymmetric-fences method. The Hidioglou-Berthelot method also includes another parameter, which is required when the difference between $E_M - E_{Q1}$ or $E_{Q3} - E_M$ is very small. I did not encounter that issue with these data, so the additional parameter is omitted here.

$$LB_E = E_M - C * (E_M - E_{Q1}) \quad (11)$$

$$UB_E = E_M + C * (E_{Q3} - E_M) \quad (12)$$

where,

LB_E is the lower boundary for the effect size.

E_M is the median effect size.

C is a hyperparameter.

E_{Q1} is the first quartile of effect sizes.

I calculated the bounds for the counts themselves using formulas provided by Belcher (2003). The lower bound is relatively straightforward.

$$LB_{HB}(Y_i) = \frac{r_M * Y_i}{1 - \frac{LB_E * E_{Q1}}{Y_i^U}} \quad (13)$$

where,

r_M is the median of r .

Y_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2014-2018 ACS five-year estimates.

X_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2009-2013 ACS five-year estimates.

LB_E is the lower boundary for the effect size.

E_{Q1} is the first quartile of effect sizes.

U is a hyperparameter.

The upper bound cannot be solved for directly and requires an iterative procedure to find an approximate solution. I used the `uniroot` function in R to apply the Newton-Raphson method using the iterative procedure described in Belcher (2003). I used the 2009-2013 ACS five-year estimate as the starting value for Z_0 . The equation for the iteration procedure is provided below. I used the default settings for the tolerance and maximum iterations.

$$UB_{HB}(Y_i):$$

$$Z_{n+1} = Z_n - \left(Z_n^{U+1} - X_i * r_M * Z_n^U - \frac{UB_E * Y_i * r_M}{(U + 1) * Z_n^U} - U * Y_i * r_M * Z_n^{U-1} \right) \quad (14)$$

where,

Z_n is the upper bound in the current iteration.

Z_{n+1} is the upper bound in the next iteration.

r_M is the median of r .

Y_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2014-2018 ACS five-year estimates.

X_i is the tract-level GQ population from the 2009-2013 ACS five-year estimates.

UB_E is the upper boundary for the effect size.

U is a hyperparameter.

4.2.1 U parameter

Figure 7 demonstrates the Hidiroglou-Berthelot bounds for different values for the U parameter – between 0.5 and 1. For each of these bounds the C parameter is held constant at a value of 200. These graphs demonstrate how the U parameter controls the shape of the bounds. With each value selected, the allowable relative change is much larger for a tract with a small GQ population than for a tract with a larger GQ population. This is the benefit of the Hidiroglou-Berthelot method. The U parameter ‘controls the importance associated with the magnitude of the data’ (Hidiroglou-Berthelot, 1986). One can see that with higher values of U , the bounds become tighter for tracts with larger GQ populations.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 7: Hidiroglou-Berthelot plausible bounds on ACS tract-level GQ population estimates for selected values of U – logarithmic scale

Table 6 and Table 7 present the metrics that were included for the other methods – the plausible bounds for different estimates and the counts of ‘out-of-bounds’ 2018 ACS GQ estimates. From Table 6, it seems that for these data, a U value of 0.5 creates bounds that are too wide.

Table 6: Hidiroglou-Berthelot plausible bounds for different tract-level GQ population estimates

Plausible Bounds - $(LB_{HB}(Y_i); UB_{HB}(Y_i))$; C value = 200						
2018 ACS						
Estimate(Y_i)	U = 0.5	U = 0.6	U = 0.7	U = 0.8	U = 0.9	U = 1
1	(0; 52)	(0; 51)	(0; 49)	(0; 48)	(0; 46)	(0; 45)
10	(0; 246)	(0; 219)	(0; 195)	(0; 176)	(0; 160)	(0; 145)
100	(3; 1,181)	(3; 963)	(3; 794)	(3; 671)	(3; 576)	(3; 498)
1,000	(77; 5,879)	(98; 4,473)	(126; 3,499)	(160; 2,843)	(198; 2,376)	(247; 2,026)
10,000	(2,104; 31,449)	(3,061; 23,297)	(4,280; 18,283)	(5,605; 15,266)	(6,852; 13,394)	(7,985; 12,223)

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Table 7: Hidiroglou-Berthelot counts of 2018 ACS tract-level GQ population estimates that are 'out-of-bounds'

2018 Tract 'Anomalies'			
C = 200			
U	Low	High	Total
0.5	240	603	843
0.6	257	610	867
0.7	268	618	886
0.8	282	627	909
0.9	305	645	950
1	329	696	1,025

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

4.2.2 C parameter

The C parameter controls the width of the Hidiroglou-Berthelot bounds. Figure 8 displays the bounds for values of C between 50 and 300. Note that the shape of the bounds remains unchanged for different values of C – the U value is held constant at 0.75.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 8: Hidiroglou-Berthelot plausible bounds on ACS tract-level GQ population estimates selected values of C – logarithmic scale

Table 8 and Table 9 present the same metrics shown previously but for differing values of the C parameter.

Table 8: Hidiroglou-Berthelot plausible bounds for different tract-level GQ population estimates

Plausible Bounds - ($LB_{HB}(Y_i); UB_{HB}(Y_i)$); U value = 0.75						
2018 ACS						
Estimate(Y_i)	C = 50	C = 100	C = 150	C = 200	C = 250	C = 300
1	(0; 22)	(0; 33)	(0; 41)	(0; 48)	(0; 55)	(0; 61)
10	(0; 87)	(0; 126)	(0; 157)	(0; 184)	(0; 208)	(0; 230)
100	(11; 365)	(6; 509)	(4; 625)	(3; 725)	(2; 815)	(2; 897)
1,000	(406; 1,834)	(251; 2,345)	(182; 2,763)	(142; 3,129)	(117; 3,458)	(99; 3,762)
10,000	(8,251; 12,458)	(6,744; 13,986)	(5,703; 15,330)	(4,940; 16,549)	(4,357; 17,674)	(3,897; 18,725)

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Table 9: Hidiroglou-Berthelot counts of 2018 ACS tract-level GQ population estimates that are ‘out-of-bounds’

2018 Tract ‘Anomalies’			
U value = 0.75			
C	Low	High	Total
50	942	795	1,737
100	535	665	1,200
150	363	630	993
200	277	619	896
250	229	616	845
300	205	610	815

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Graphically, the Hidiroglou-Berthelot method seems suitable for drawing plausible bounds for the GQ data. However, the results in Table 8 show bounds that are still imprecise. It appears the method is accurately capturing the large amount of variation in GQ estimates from period to period for the tracts. Therefore, it may prove useful to group the tracts in order to better capture variation that is ‘typical’ in tract of a given type.

5. Grouping Tracts

In establishment surveys, these outlier-detection methods are usually applied by industry type. Assuming tracts with different GQ types would behave in different ways, I sought to group the tracts by GQ type. However, tracts can contain a varied mix of GQ types. As a first pass at grouping the tracts, I took a business rules approach, using the 2010 Census Summary File 1 (SF1). The SF1 includes counts for each tract by GQ type.

First, for each GQ type in Table 1, I calculated quartiles of the population in each tract. I removed the tracts with zero population in the given GQ type before calculating the quartiles. I used these quartiles to create the business rules, starting with GQ types that tend to have larger populations in a given area.

In group 1, I included tracts that had a GQ population greater than the 25th percentile in correctional facilities for adults. Group 2 contains any tracts not in group 1, that had a college population greater than the 75th percentile in colleges among all tracts. From the remaining tracts, I included in group 3 any tracts that a population in colleges greater than the 25th percentile of the college population among all tracts. I continued on in the same manner, assigning tracts to groups according to the criteria in Table 10.

Table 10: Business rules for grouping tracts by GQ type

Group	Number of Tracts	Description
Group 1	3,563	Correctional Facilities for Adults > P25
Group 2	840	College Housing > P75
Group 3	1,613	College Housing > P25
Group 4	286	Military Group Quarters > P25
Group 5	3,324	Nursing Facilities > P75
Group 6	6,781	Nursing Facilities > P25
Group 7	1,143	Juvenile Facilities or Other Health Care Facilities > P75
Group 8	2,270	Juvenile Facilities or Other Health Care Facilities > P25
Group 9	4,861	Other Noninstitutionalized GQs > P75
Group 10	10,929	Other Noninstitutionalized GQs > P25
Group 11	9,795	All other with 2010 Census GQ population > 0
Group 12	28,146	All other tracts

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2010 Census, Summary File 1

After assigning tracts to groups, I wanted to compare methods by determining bounds that would flag roughly the same number of anomalies. In order to do this, I wrote functions that would flag about 0.5% of tracts in each group. I chose this small percentage so that the bounds would be close to the edges of the distribution. Flagging a larger proportion of anomalies would cause tighter bounds and imply that there is a larger number of anomalies in the ACS data. However, some number of anomalies must be flagged, otherwise the bounds would be too wide to be useful.

For the OLS method, the function starts with a value of $d = 0.5$. For each group, the total number of tracts is used to calculate how many outliers are needed for roughly 0.5% of the tracts to be flagged. For example, for group 1, $0.005 * 3,563 \approx 17.8$. The value of d is increased by 0.5 until fewer than 17 outliers are flagged. That is, the bounds are made wider, so fewer and fewer anomalies are flagged until less than 0.5% have been flagged. The function was applied for every group. A ceiling for d is set to 15.

The same idea was applied for the asymmetric-fences method. Starting with $k = 0.5$, the value of k was increased by 0.5 until less than 0.5% of the tracts in the group were flagged as anomalies. Again, a ceiling is applied, with k limited to be less than or equal to 15.

For the Hidiroglou-Berthelot method, the C value was increased starting with a value of 5 and increasing by increments of 5 until less than 0.5% of the tracts were flagged as anomalies. The upper limit for the C value is 300. The U value was held constant at 0.75.

The next three figures present the bounds for each group. The OLS and Hidiroglou-Berthelot bounds appear to work well across groups. This shows that for these methods, hyperparameters could be chosen based on the number or proportion of anomalies are to be flagged and reviewed.

However, this level of automation does not seem to work for the Asymmetric-Fences bounds. For some groups, the square root transformation did not sufficiently correct the skewness of the ratios. As a result, LB_R , the lower bound for the square root of the ratio becomes negative even for low values of k . For groups 4, 11, and 12, the k parameter reached the upper limit of 15 before less than 0.5% of tracts were out of bounds. Because the value of k is large, the magnitude of LB_R is also large. When the reverse transformation is applied and it is squared, the bound for the lower ratio becomes similar to the bound for the upper ratio, causing the problematic bounds seen. For groups 7, 8, and 10, LB_R is negative, but less than one. Therefore, when it is squared, it is closer to zero and the resulting lower bound is zero for all but very large values of Y_i . Alternate transformations, such as the log transformation would have worked better for these groups. Therefore, in order to automate

the selection of hyperparameters for this method, one would need to also automate the selection of the transforming function.

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates; 2010 Census, Summary File 1

Figure 9: Grouped tracts with OLS plausible bounds – d value determined by flagging 0.5% of tracts in each group

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates; 2010 Census, Summary File 1

Figure 10: Grouped tracts with asymmetric fences plausible bounds – k value determined by flagging 0.5% of tracts in each group

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates; 2010 Census, Summary File 1

Figure 11: Grouped tracts with Hidiroglou-Berthelot plausible bounds – C value determined by flagging 0.5% of tracts in each group

6. Summary

The OLS and Hidiroglou-Berthelot methods offer the most promise as methods for flagging anomalies in GQ data. As expected, there are some similarities between the GQ population estimates and the economic data where these methods originated. In particular, GQ population estimates are highly skewed, with most tracts having a very small number or no people living in group quarters while relatively few tracts have a large GQ population.

However, counts of GQ people in tracts between time periods do not necessarily behave in the same way as revenue or expenses for businesses. The relative differences across time may not be informative across tracts as they are for businesses. It may be the case that the GQ population in certain tracts is quite stable while it is quite variable in others. For that reason, the grouping of the tracts used in calculating the bounds may be more important than the outlier-detection method that is applied. For instance, if we chose OLS or simply set an absolute limit on the allowable difference in a tract from the latest ACS estimate, it would be advisable to set that limit based on whether the GQ population within the tract resides in a correctional facility, college dorms, or nursing homes. Future work should focus on more sophisticated methods of grouping the tracts.

The selection of hyperparameters for these methods can be automated based on the number or proportion of anomalies to be flagged. Given that automated bounds would not require as much review, the tracts can be categorized into a large number of groups that are smaller and homogeneous in terms of GQ types or other characteristics that may be predictive of variation in the GQ population over time.

Additionally, future work should consider setting more than one hyperparameter for a given group of tracts. For example, separate hyperparameters could be chosen for creating upper and lower bounds, or separate hyperparameters assigned by the relative magnitude of the GQ population in the group. Another alternative to explore would be applying stricter criteria but only reviewing anomalies flagged by multiple methods.

7. References

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Appendix

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 12: Tract-level GQ population estimates from five-year American Community Survey

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 13: OLS regression plausible bounds on ACS tract-level GQ population estimates for selected values of d

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 14: Asymmetric fences plausible bounds on ACS tract-level GQ population estimates for selected values of k

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 15: Hidiroglou-Berthelot plausible bounds on ACS tract-level GQ population estimates for selected values of U

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2009-2013 and 2014-2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates

Figure 16: Hidioglou-Berthelot plausible bounds on ACS tract-level GQ population estimates for selected values of C